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How much water is used by a black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia* L.) short-rotation plantation on degraded soil?

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Introduction

Robinia pseudoacacia L. is an autochthonous North American tree species, where its distribution ranges from a humid to sub-humid climate. As an early successional and nitrogen-fixing species, black locust grows rapidly as a pioneer tree species under a wide range of site condition and it is considered a drought tolerant tree species (VESTE and KRIEBITZSCH, 2010). In southern Brandenburg these trees have been successfully used in short-rotation plantations for land reclamation and biomass production in recultivated open-cast lignite mining areas, where nutrients and water resources are limited (BÖHM et al., 2009). Short-rotation plantations for bioenergy production are raising interest, particularly for those areas where conventional crop systems are economically not profitable. Furthermore woody crops have a high benefit for landscape restoration (QUICKENSTEIN et al., 2009, DILLY et al., 2010, VESTE et al., 2010).

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Since the availability of water and nutrition is limiting the primary production (Sinclair et al. 2005), a key open question is the water use of the trees under different soil water contents. Additionally, the ecophysiological response of the plants to different water availability is investigated by using a portable gas exchange system, which allows the measurement of transpiration rate and net photosynthesis. In our experiment water use at whole plant level is linked to the biomass production and ecophysiological performance.

Key words: Bioenergy production, short-rotation plantation, water use, ecophysiological response, yield-transpiration relation.

Material and methods

Two years old black locust trees have been selected from the recultivated post-mining area in Welzow, near Cottbus, Brandenburg, where *R. pseudoacacia* L. are established as a short-rotation plantation for bioenergy production. The experiment is carried out by using wicked lysimeters with three replicate for each treatment. The three treatments have different irrigation regimes, which are related to the soil water content at 20 cm depth (7%, 10% and 14%) (Fig. 1).

Fig.1 Black locust established in wicker lysimeters at soil water content mean 14%

A critical problem with zero tension lysimeters is that saturation at the bottom layer can occur, (BEN-GAL and SHANI, 2002). In those conditions the roots are exposed to oxygen restraint and anaerobic processes may take place. A cost efficient solution is provided by wick lysimeters (BEN-GAL and SHANI, 2002), in which a constant suction at the bottom layer is exerted by a high conductive drainage extension. Our lysimeters (MANTOVANI et al., 2011) consist of 70x50 cm polyethylene drums filled with sandy soil at bulk density 1.3 (Fig. 1). To avoid saturation at the bottom layer, a polyethylene extension pipe filled with rockwool has been installed at bottom of the lysimeter. Roots are prevented from growing into the drainage extension by fitting in a roots stop geotextile. Flax continuity at the interlayer rockwool-geotextile is guaranteed by an interposed 5 cm tick soil layer. The water amounts are controlled by an automatic drip irrigation system and supplied in relation to the volumetric soil water content. The lysimeters are installed under a light transmissive roof to avoid uncontrolled water input. The soil water content and soil matrix potential variations are determined at two depths 20 and 40cm deep respectively by a TDR (Time Domain Reflectometry) device (SM 200, Soil Moisture Sensor, Delta-T Devices, Cambridge) and a gypsum tensiometer (SIS, UMS, München). Soil water content along all the profile (every 10 cm) has been recorded weekly by a profile probe (PR2/4w-02, Delta-T). Soil temperature has been recorded at 20 cm depth by a thermistor (SKTS 200, Skye Instruments Ltd, Powys). A schematic diagram of the system is shown in figure 2. The transpiration is calculated from the experimental water balance daily, and the plant growth rate is evaluated monthly by allometric measurements. The trunk diameter increase of the trees are measured daily by dendrometers (DD-S, Ecomatik, Dachau).

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of the lysimeter and irrigation system

Photosynthesis is the essential process for biomass productivity. CO_2 uptake and water loss are controlled by the stomata on the leaf level. In order to evaluate ecophysiological performance of Robinia we measured the net photosynthesis and transpiration of fully expanded leaves with a minicuvette system (CMS 400, Heinz Walz Effeltrich, Germany) under constant light conditions (approx. $1200 \text{ mmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and temperature (20° , 25°C , 32°C). The air humidity was similar to ambient conditions. CO_2 and H_2O fluxes were determined with an infra-red gas analyzer (BINOS 100-4P, Rosemount, Hanau, Germany) and expressed on the projected leaf area.

Results and Discussion

The amount of water used by the plants grown under different irrigation regimes with the SWC mean at 7%, 10% and 14%, from the June 1st to August 30 estimated from the experimental water balance is shown in figure 3.

Fig. 3 Cumulative water use of individual tree at different soil water conditions from 1 June to 30 August 2011.

At the whole plant level, differences in terms of mean relative length increments between the treatments are significant only during the last period of growth (Fig. 4A). The relative diameter increase is shown in figure 4B.

Fig. 4 Mean relative plant increase A) length B) diameter, from 1 June to 30 August 2011.

At the leaf level, transpiration and net CO₂ exchange is reduced in trees with a soil water content of 7% due to stomata closure (Fig. 5). This response of the stomata was more pronounced during days with high temperature and high water vapour pressure

deficit (vpd) to minimise water loss. However, during hot days (32°) transpiration of the well-watered trees are not controlled by stomata and increased with increasing vpd (Fig. 5A). Furthermore, the net photosynthesis rate is lower in the SWC 7% treatment compared with the other two treatments as a result of lower leaf conductance (Fig. 5B).

Fig. 5 Transpiration (A) and net CO₂ exchange (B) of *R. pseudoacacia* L. under different soil water and climatic conditions. VPD = Water vapour deficit.

Conclusion

The growth of the trees with the volumetric soil water content mean of 7%, 10% and 14% used 132, 187 and 311 liters of water, respectively. At the whole plant level, the well-watered plants (14%) produced a significant length increase only during the last period of growth (from August 1st to 30) by using approximately three times the water used by the trees grown at lower irrigation amount. Furthermore at the leaf level the increase of transpiration is not followed by an increasing of photosynthesis. As a result *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. cannot be considered a water saving tree.

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